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Estimating and understanding crop yields with explainable deep learning in the Indian Wheat Belt

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Estimating and understanding crop yields with explainable deep learning in the Indian Wheat Belt

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Supplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Abstract

Forecasting crop yields is becoming increasingly important under the current context in which food security needs to be ensured despite the challenges brought by climate change, an expanding world population accompanied by rising incomes, increasing soil erosion, and decreasing water resources. Temperature, radiation, water availability and other environmental conditions influence crop growth, development, and final grain yield in a complex nonlinear manner. Machine learning (ML) techniques, and deep learning (DL) methods in particular, can account for such nonlinear relations between yield and its covariates. However, they typically lack transparency and interpretability, since the way the predictions are derived is not directly evident. Yet, in the context of yield forecasting, understanding which are the underlying factors behind both a predicted loss or gain is of great relevance. Here, we explore how to benefit from the increased predictive performance of DL methods while maintaining the ability to interpret how the models achieve their results. To do so, we applied a deep neural network to multivariate time series of vegetation and meteorological data to estimate the wheat yield in the Indian Wheat Belt. Then, we visualized and analyzed the features and yield drivers learned by the model with the use of regression activation maps. The DL model outperformed other tested models (ridge regression and random forest) and facilitated the interpretation of variables and processes that lead to yield variability. The learned features were mostly related to the length of the growing season, and temperature and light conditions during this time. For example, our results showed that high yields in 2012 were associated with low temperatures accompanied by sunny conditions during the growing period. The proposed methodology can be used for other crops and regions in order to facilitate application of DL models in agriculture.

1. Introduction

The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations estimates that 50% more food needs to be produced by 2050 in order to feed the increasing world population (FAO 2017). However, the ongoing

efforts to increase food production are curbed by climate change, which has already impacted global mean yields of major crops in the last decades, and is further projected to negatively affect food security (FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO 2018, Mbow *et al* 2019). It is therefore crucial to not only accurately

predict crop yield, but also to model and characterize the processes involved by understanding the meteorological drivers of crop yield variability.

Meteorological variables influence crop growth, development, and final grain yield in a nonlinear manner and often with complex interactions (Siebert *et al* 2017, Akter and Rafiqul Islam 2017). These variables are accounted for in both process-based as well as statistical models to estimate crop yield (e.g. Lobell *et al* 2011, Iizumi *et al* 2018). While process-based models require detailed (and not always available) information on the farmers' practices, recent increase in the availability of global satellite observations and advancements in statistical methods have fueled the application of machine learning (ML) models at various scales (e.g. Lobell *et al* 2011, Guan *et al* 2017, Cai *et al* 2019). In particular, such models may have the capability of accounting for additional factors reducing growth and yield (e.g. pests, diseases, weeds and other perils).

In order to better exploit the wealth of information in the meteorological and satellite-derived vegetation data, we propose to apply convolutional neural networks (CNNs), a class of deep learning (DL) models (Goodfellow *et al* 2016, LeCun *et al* 2015). DL methods promise great advances in Earth observation and geosciences (Reichstein *et al* 2019), as they can account for the large size of the input datasets, nonlinear relations, and interconnections among multiple variables. Since CNNs can learn the features directly from the data, this approach does not depend on the manual selection of specific parameters.

A major shortcoming of ML methods in general, and of DL methods in particular, is that the learned relations are hidden under very complicated prediction functions. However, recent years have seen the emergence of a whole field of ML called 'Explainable Artificial Intelligence' to face this issue (Miller 2019), and techniques and methodologies have been introduced to study what the ML/DL models are learning (Montavon *et al* 2018). In this work, we focus on an efficient method to explain the model predictions called regression activation mapping (RAM) (Zhou *et al* 2016, Wang *et al* 2017, Wang and Yang 2017). RAM contains the immediate information for the final prediction, but also maintains the correspondence to the input data in the time (or spatial) dimension and shows the contribution of each time (or space) instant to the final output. As a result, we not only benefit from DL in terms of improvements in the model performance, but we specifically focus on evaluating the underlying drivers, thereby placing confidence in the model as well as gaining insight into the relevant conditions leading to crop yield variability.

Here, we focus on the wheat yield estimation in the Indian Wheat Belt, where concerns of yield stagnation have risen due to increasingly inconsistent growth trend of wheat yields in recent years (Ray *et al* 2012, Tripathi and Mishra 2017). High temperature has

been identified as the most detrimental factor, affecting both crop growth and grain formation (Lobell *et al* 2012, Jain *et al* 2017), but also heavy and untimely rainfall and hailstorm events have caused large-scale damages to the crops (Singh *et al* 2017). Finally, cloudy weather with high humidity and low temperatures increases chances of wheat diseases (e.g. wheat rusts and spot blotch) (Duveiller *et al* 2007, Kaur *et al* 2015), which have been spreading in India (Hodson 2011). In addition, in the specific case of the double cropping system in India (typically rice-wheat), the timing of wheat sowing may be suboptimal because it is conditioned by local farming practices and by the timing of the rice harvest (Global Information and Early Warning System on Food and Agriculture (GIEWS) 2019). As the Indian Wheat Belt poses many challenges regarding complex processes and nonlinearities, it constitutes a good scenario to evaluate our approach that could be eventually used in other similar settings.

Therefore, the aims of the paper are two-fold: (1) to develop a DL model for wheat yield estimation and evaluate its application for within-season yield forecast, and (2) to scrutinize what this model learned by visualizing and interpreting the drivers of yield estimation. This knowledge extraction process may have implications in further crop management actions, as well as interactions with stakeholders and farmers.

2. Materials and methods

Our analysis was performed in the Indian Wheat Belt region, which supplies around 70% of India's total wheat production (figure 1). We estimated district-level crop yield using as input a set of time series of meteorological and satellite-derived vegetation variables at a daily resolution that are summarized in table 1 and described in S1. In our analysis, we used three vegetation indices (VIs): the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) (Tucker *et al* 1985), the normalized difference water index (NDWI) (Gao 1996), and near-infrared reflectance of vegetation (NIRv) (Badgley *et al* 2017); and seven environmental variables: minimum, mean and maximum air temperatures (T_{\min} , T_{mean} , T_{\max}), downward short-wave radiation flux (SW_{down}), water vapor pressure deficit (VPD), precipitation, and day-length (table 1). Pixel level values of input variables were spatially aggregated to the district level as the weighted average according to fractional area occupied by wheat in each pixel (S1 in the supplementary information, available online at stacks.iop.org/ERL/15/024019/mmedia).

The DL models (CNN) and the baseline models (ridge regression, RR, and random forest, RF) were trained and tested on the dataset of 143 districts over 13 years (2001–2013) (S2). The time range of the analysis was determined by the availability of both MODIS imagery and wheat yield data for all states. In the standard setup, all districts were pooled together

and a separate model for each year was calculated, where data from this year were used for testing and data from the rest of the years were used for training.

The CNN model stacked one-dimensional convolutional layers (Conv1D) along time dimension and max pooling layers (MaxPool1D) with a window size of five (figure 2(a)). After the second Conv1D, the data were fed into a global average pooling layer (GAP), which computed the mean in the time dimension for each variable. Finally, a simple linear layer was applied to obtain the final yield prediction.

We propose to use RAMs as a tool to visualize and interpret how the CNN models achieve their results. Activation mapping has been previously applied for image analysis in the classification (Zhou *et al* 2016) and regression problems (Wang and Yang 2017). Here, we show their application on time series data, as inspired by the application of class activation map to interpret the temporal data in Wang *et al* (2017). For a time series input, the RAM is another time series such that its average over time (plus bias) corresponds to the predicted output value. As a result, RAM contains the immediate information for the final prediction, but also maintains the correspondence between the last convolutional feature maps and the input data in the time dimension. RAM is calculated by combining the convoluted data that is fed into GAP layer with the weights of the final linear layer (figure 2(b)). In particular, if $\{z_{1,t}, \dots, z_{d,t}\}$ are the input time series to the GAP layer, the output of the GAP layer is the mean over the time dimension $\frac{1}{T} \sum_t z_{i,t}$ for each time series $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$. The final yield prediction (\hat{y}) is then the linear combination of those averaged time series:

$$\hat{y} = \sum_i^d \left(\frac{1}{T} \sum_t z_{i,t} \right) w_{z,i} + b_z, \quad (1)$$

where $w_{z,i}$ and b_z are respectively the weights and the bias of the output linear combination. In this setting, we define the RAM (r_t) as the following time series:

$$r_t = \sum_i^d z_{i,t} w_{z,i}. \quad (2)$$

RAM satisfies that $\hat{y} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_t r_t + b_z$. Hence the RAM value at a given time step r_t can be interpreted as an estimation of the derivative of the output w.r.t. time, $r_t \approx d\hat{y}/dt$, and the final estimation as the integral of RAM, $\hat{y} = \frac{1}{T} \int r(t) dt$.

The models were applied directly to the multivariate time series of input variables (VIs and meteorological data). The time period analyzed corresponded to 245 days, starting from October 1st, that cover the *rabi* growing season when wheat is grown. As a result, each input for the DL model was a tensor of size $(245, n_{vars})$, where n_{vars} is a number of input variables that varied depending on the experiment. In case of the baseline models, the daily data was reshaped into vectors (of length $245 \times n_{vars}$). Afterwards the baseline models were trained using those vectors as input and the final yield as output. Application of RR and RF to monthly averages slightly increased model performance (S3).

The model performances were compared among CNNs, as well as the baseline models for three different combinations of the input data, with two, five or ten input variables using the time series data only ('No district'), as well as using additionally the district information as input ('Incl. district') as in a mixed-effects model (Wu 2009). Specifically, in the 'Incl. district' setting, we added a district-dependent bias in the last layer of the

Table 1. Main characteristics of the data used in this study. Most of the data was downloaded using the Google Earth Engine (GEE) cloud computing platform (Gorelick *et al* 2017).

Category	Variables	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Source
Satellite observations of vegetation	NDVI, NDWI, NIRv calculated from MODIS Bands 1, 2 and 7	500 m	16 day resolution, 1 day sampling	MODIS MCD43A4 V6, exported from GEE
Meteorological data	T_{\min} , T_{mean} , T_{\max} , SW_{down} , VPD	0.25°	3 h, aggregated to daily values	GLDAS-2.1, exported from GEE
	Precipitation	0.05°	Daily	CHIRPS, exported from GEE
	Day-length	District	Daily	Calculated between civil twilight before the sunrise and the end of civil twilight after the sunset
Crop fraction	<i>Rabi</i> season wheat crop fraction	5000 m	Yearly	Annual Cropland Datasets of National Remote Sensing Centre in India
Wheat yield data	<i>Rabi</i> season wheat yield	District	Yearly	Indiastat

CNN model that was fitted during the training process. The district information was represented in RR as an additional binary class matrix, and in RF—as a categorical variable. The best model architectures and hyperparameters were determined as described in S3. In addition, we compared the model performance to the null model, in which the yield for each district for every year was calculated as the average of yields from the other available years in the input dataset for this district (e.g. yield for the district Patiala in 2006 was calculated as the mean of yields in Patiala for years 2003–2005 and 2007–2013). As a next step, to evaluate what input parameters were the most important for the wheat yield estimation, we run ensembles of five CNN models in two simple sets of varying combinations of input variables: (1) with one variable only (for all ten variables); and (2) with two variables: VI + one meteorological parameter (21 combinations).

Finally, two models were selected for RAM calculations and visualizations: CNN with two input variables, NDWI and T_{\min} (CNN₂), as well as all ten input variables (CNN₁₀), both including district information. These models were run in model ensembles of ten members each. In addition to creating a separate model for each year (as previously), we also re-trained these models on all the input data (CNN_{2,all} and CNN_{10,all}) in order to compare RAMs across different years created with the same model weights.

Because our study compares many different models, we chose to use a single evaluation metric to simplify the process of model selection and the presentation of the results. The selected metric is the

Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) (Nash and Sutcliffe 1970), that provides an indication of the goodness of fit and can range from $-\infty$ to 1, with the best possible score (1.0) meaning that modeled crop yields are equal to reported ones.

3. Results

3.1. Performance of the models

The performances measured as NSE for different models and input datasets are compared for all years averaged and for one year separately (2012) in table 2. The results for 2012 were shown to demonstrate that the overall good performance among all years does not necessarily guarantee accurate predictions for abnormal years. 2012 was a peculiar year characterized by very high yields compared to average (figure S8), as indicated by poor performance of the null model (table 2). CNN models provided the best results overall (best NSE of 0.868 among all years in the ‘Incl. district’ setting, compared to the best NSE of 0.757 for RR and 0.836 for RF) that were stable among model runs (S4), which shows applicability of such models to dense time series for yield estimation. The null model was already a good predictor for the yield among all years (NSE of 0.812) and it performed better than any model that excluded district information, as the majority of the yield variation came from the spatial variation (S5). However, when considering the abnormal year 2012, the null model performed much worse than the other models (NSE of 0.288), which demonstrates the

Table 2. Yield estimation performance for the test sub-sets using CNNs, ridge regression and random forest at their best performing architectures for different input variables combinations: 2 input vars. (NDVI + T_{\min}), 5 input vars. (NDVI, NDWI, T_{\min} , SW_{down}, VPD), 10 input vars. (NDVI, NDWI, NIRv, T_{\min} , T_{mean} , T_{max} , SW_{down}, VPD, precipitation, day-length). Excluding or including district information (+ district) refers to ‘No district’ or ‘Incl. district’ settings, respectively.

Model	input vars.	NSE	
		All years	2012
CNN	2	0.663	0.251
CNN	5	0.740	0.494
CNN	10	0.788	0.625
CNN	2 + district	0.830	0.532
CNN	5 + district	0.862	0.741
CNN	10 + district	0.868	0.743
RR	2	0.734	0.418
RR	5	0.744	0.436
RR	10	0.756	0.432
RR	2 + district	0.737	0.421
RR	5 + district	0.746	0.438
RR	10 + district	0.757	0.434
RF	2	0.704	0.338
RF	5	0.744	0.443
RF	10	0.754	0.481
RF	2 + district	0.827	0.493
RF	5 + district	0.831	0.480
RF	10 + district	0.836	0.453
Null model ^a		0.812	0.288

^a Null model is calculated for each district for every year as the average of yields from the remaining available years in this district.

importance of using satellite observations to estimate yields for atypical years.

3.2. Impact of input variables on the model performance

Performance of CNNs improved with the increase in the number of input parameters, both in terms of the best performing models, as well as among all tested model settings (table 2). When testing models with one or two variables to evaluate the parameters importance, the model performance and variable ranking were not consistent among the years, with 2012 showing the worst performance (figures 3 and 4). The models performed much better and had a smaller performance variation if the information on the district was included. However, in 2012, some model combinations gave better results without district information, which is related to the fact that the null model performed poorly for this year.

In case of models with one variable only and no district information (‘No district’ in figure 3), VIs performed better among all the parameters (and NDWI the best). Models with day-length as the only variable had a very good performance, even though this

parameter does not carry any information about the crop condition. It suggests that the model was actually trying to learn the specific day-length patterns related to districts, as yields have a clear spatial pattern in this region (figure 1) that is somewhat similar to the latitudinal distribution of day-length (figure S9).

When the district information was fed into the model (‘Incl. district’ in figure 3), the best performing model across all years was the one using NDWI, followed closely by SW_{down} and other VIs. The good performance of NDWI and SW_{down} was reproduced for models with two variables (figure 4). However, this behavior was not consistent among all the years for neither one- nor two-variable models. Good performance of NDWI and SW_{down} in 2012 (figures 3 and 4) could be a leading factor responsible for their high overall ranking, as the differences among the models in this year were much larger than for other years. For example, in case of 2002, the ranking of pairs including NDWI and SW_{down} were among the worst, but the general variability was very small. These results suggest that accounting for various parameters is important, as the conditions that limit or boost the crop yields vary among the years.

3.3. RAMs and their sensitivity to input variables

Overall, the main features of RAMs were the same for all the ensemble members (figure 5), as well as for the models re-trained on all the input data (CNN_{2,all} and CNN_{10,all}). We compare in detail RAMs of the district Patiala for 2006, for selected CNN models using two (CNN_{2,all}) or ten (CNN_{10,all}) input variables in figures 6(a)–(b). As mentioned before, the average of RAM plus bias (bias both of the whole model and the district-specific, see S6), equals the estimated yield. Even though RAMs are products of the complex nonlinear interactions of the input data, some basic patterns can be directly inferred. For example, the overall shape of RAMs is closely related to the growing cycle as shown by NDWI. In case of the 2-variable model (figure 6(a)), all observed temporal patterns of RAM can be related to NDWI or T_{\min} , as these were the only input parameters. As a result, a small dip in RAM around day 100 can be associated with the increase in T_{\min} , as NDWI during this time was steadily increasing, which suggests the negative impact of higher T_{\min} on the crop yield. To support this claim, we modified T_{\min} and calculated the resulting changes in RAMs as shown in figure 6(c). Two small changes were performed on the T_{\min} data—in the first case we removed the T_{\min} peak around day 100 (shown in blue in figure 6(c)) and in the second case, we increased T_{\min} around day 150 (shown in yellow in figure 6(c)). The changes in the resulting RAMs—which directly relate to changes in the estimated yield—are highlighted in blue and yellow in figure 6(c). The decrease in T_{\min} led to the increase in RAM and removed the previously observed dip. On the other hand, increase in T_{\min} led to a similar decrease in RAM,

Figure 3. Model performance (NSE) for ensembles of five CNN models with only one variable as the input for selected years and averaged among all years. The results for two model settings are tested: ‘No district’ is using only one bias in the whole model in the final layers, while in case of ‘Incl. district’ a bias per district (time-independent) is additionally fitted during the training process.

Figure 4. Model performance (NSE) for ensembles of five CNN models with only two input variables (VI + meteorological variable) for selected years and averaged among all years. Only results for models including district information (‘Incl. district’) are shown.

Figure 5. Variability of regression activation maps calculated for different districts and years for different members in a model ensemble of ten with ten input variables (a)–(c) or in a model ensemble of ten with two input variables (d)–(f). The thin green lines (‘one year’) correspond to models calculated for one year using other years as training, red lines (‘all years’) correspond to models trained on the whole dataset, while the thick dashed lines (Mean of ‘all years’) correspond to the average of the ‘all years’ models.

and therefore a decrease in the yield. However, analogous T_{\min} modifications for CNN_{10,all} resulted in different magnitudes of changes in RAMs due to decrease or increase in T_{\min} . The increase in T_{\min} towards the end of the growing season had a much bigger impact on RAM than the decrease in T_{\min} earlier in the growing season, which led to a positive but very small change in RAM.

To better identify the parameters and features that led to certain responses in RAMs, we compared selected input variables and RAMs for Patiala for two very different years: the year 2006, when the yield was quite poor (4.233 t/ha), and 2012, when the yield was very good (5.473 t/ha) in figures 7(a) and (b). In 2006, RAM demonstrated overall lower values and many strong drops, while in 2012, RAM showed consistently high values despite not much higher VIs. To analyze the drivers of this variability, we exchanged, one in turn, four input variables (T_{\min} , T_{\max} , SW_{down} , precipitation) among 2006 and 2012 to check how this would affect changes in both RAMs and estimated yields (figures 7(c)–(j)). For example, SW_{down} was mostly responsible for creating the dips in RAMs in 2006 for Patiala—as many of them were filled when SW_{down} from 2012 was used, especially the big drop around day 160 (figure 7(g)). Overall, the yield in 2006 increased using any of the input parameters from 2012, but the highest increase was observed for T_{\max} , followed by SW_{down} , T_{\min} and only slightly for precipitation. The same rank of variables in terms of the magnitude of the impact was observed in the case of modifying the input variables in 2012.

Similar features were consistent among all districts in 2006 and 2012, as shown by anomalies (positive in red, negative in blue) in RAM, NDWI, T_{\max} , T_{\min} and SW_{down} in figure 8. In general, these years were relatively sunny, but in 2012, both T_{\max} and T_{\min} had strong negative anomalies during the second half of the growing season. The rapid and short negative anomalies in RAMs were usually related to negative

anomalies in SW_{down} (highlighted with green boxes), which sometimes were also accompanied by positive anomalies in T_{\min} (as cloudy skies capture the long-wave radiation emitted by Earth at night). It is noted that this link may lead to a wrong interpretation of the effect of T_{\min} , when considered alone (e.g. a model with T_{\min} as the only weather input). Positive anomalies in RAM in 2012 were connected to strong negative anomalies in T_{\max} and T_{\min} (highlighted with magenta boxes).

3.4. Predictive skill of CNNs

We examined if our CNN model could be potentially useful for predicting the yield during the growing season by analyzing the impact of shortening the input time series in 25-day steps on the model performance. As compared to the null model, CNN₁₀ had better prediction from day 145, which corresponds to the last week of February (figure 9). In general, the month of February is the time of the anthesis stage, conditions during which are crucial for the final crop yield. Therefore, covering this time period is essential for a good yield estimation. From day 195 (middle of April), which widely corresponds to the harvest time in this region, the model performance did not increase. This suggests that after harvest the additional data were not useful anymore for the yield estimation. Although this may seem trivial, it is nevertheless important that model performance appears insensitive to post-harvest data, as adding such data could occur whilst in an operational context.

4. Discussion

4.1. Application of DL models for yield estimation

Even though our DL modeling approach was constrained by the requirement for network explainability (global pooling layer after the convolutional layers to facilitate RAMs), it outperformed RF and RR in the

yield estimation task, though RF provided a strong performance improvement as compared to RR. Although DL models are already widely used for a variety of problems in image and signal processing domain (LeCun *et al* 2015), DL applications for crop yield estimation are still rare (e.g. You *et al* 2017, Crane-Droesch 2018), as the transfer of available tools from the field of ML into the environmental applications requires adaptations that account for specificities of the data. Our results demonstrate that CNNs can be a valid tool for capturing complex processes in agricultural systems, and their application can be therefore further explored for other crops and regions.

4.2. Impact of environmental conditions on the crop yield as captured by DL

To generalize well in the yield estimation problem, it is important to train models over several years and simultaneously account for multiple vegetation and

environmental variables, as the main yield drivers vary among seasons. Since many of the input variables in the crop yield models are correlated and inter-related, multiple parameters should be considered when trying to understand the impact of variables on the crop yield in the model. For example, the impact of T_{min} varied depending on whether it was the only input meteorological variable or one of many (figure 6).

RAM's general shape reflected VIs, which emphasizes the importance of the length of the growing period and agrees with previous studies (Lobell *et al* 2012, Jain *et al* 2017). Meteorological variables used together with VIs are expected to have only a marginal contribution to yield estimation, as their impact is already reflected by vegetation growth that is captured by VIs. Overall, SW_{down} turned out to be the most important meteorological variable for yield estimation, even though the ranking varied significantly among the years. Comparison of performances among models

with one or two input variables, as well as the RAM analysis, showed that high yields in 2012 were associated with low temperatures accompanied by sunny conditions during the growing period, though most recent studies focus primarily on the impact of increasing temperatures in the Indian Wheat Belt (e.g. Duncan *et al* 2014, Jain *et al* 2017, Song *et al* 2018) and in other regions (Lobell *et al* 2005). As an important driver of photosynthesis, SW_{down} affects the resources

that crops can build during the growing season, which is apparently not fully reflected in the VIs. High radiation levels are also especially important during the critical period for grain number determination (20–30 days before anthesis to ten days afterwards) (Fischer 1985). Analysis of RAMs showed that the model was trained to recognize events of decreased light as having negative impact on the crop yield, which suggests that the decline of photosynthesis due

to decreased radiation was larger than the benefit due to increased diffused light. This agrees with the negative effects associated with a reduction in sunlight shown on a global scale (Proctor *et al* 2018). Decreased penetration of sunlight for the crop has already spurred demand for breeding for high photosynthetic or radiation-use efficiency (Joshi *et al* 2007). These observations also suggest that sun-induced fluorescence could be a good direct proxy for the crop yield, as it carries information on light conditions, and was previously shown to perform better than VIs for yield estimation (Song *et al* 2018). Although NIRv was found superior to other VIs for estimating GPP (Badgley *et al* 2017), we did not detect any benefit of using it for the yield estimation.

4.3. Physical interpretability of RAMs

The novelty of our approach extends beyond obtaining a satisfactory model performance, as we adapted the activation mapping to the regression problem for the temporal data in order to localize important patterns for the yield estimation. The analysis of RAMs applied in the time dimension facilitates DL network interpretability and provides the needed transparency on what DL models learn and how they accomplish their prediction. Analysis of the different patterns in RAMs can provide a consistent description of how the network captures the weather effects in relation to the temporal progression of the crop, and can ultimately lead to a valid physical interpretation. The natural way to interpret RAMs is to regard it as a kind of derivative of the yield function in time. In the global pooling layer this function is then integrated out by the network to estimate the crop yield, which as a result reflects the accumulated effects of crop growth and meteorological conditions. Thus, the application of RAM allows for an instinctive analysis of how certain events in the time domain impact the estimated crop yield and enables a comparison with known drivers. In our case, RAMs were roughly reflecting the development of the crop and at the same time were sensitive to the variability of meteorological conditions, which somehow reflects the basic approach of relating yield to the accumulated biomass. Such an approach can increase the confidence in the model (as it captures the processes that are expected to be relevant), but might also draw attention to so far neglected features or model weaknesses. For example, although high temperatures leading to low yields are often considered in the Indian Wheat Belt, the importance of sunny conditions for good yields is rather neglected. On the other hand, RAMs varying towards the end of the analyzed time period might suggest that the model has not completely learned to ignore the time after the harvest. In general, the proposed methodology facilitates the application of DL in agriculture, not only to improve yield estimation and prediction but also to gain insight into the key drivers of crop yield.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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